

Electronic and transport properties of 2D YSe and its tetragonal phase via density functional theory

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Abstract: The electronic structure and transport coefficients of 2D YSe and its tetragonal haeckelite phase have been investigated using Density Functional Theory (DFT) and Boltzmann transport theory within the constant relaxation time approximation. Both phases exhibit metallic behavior, with the Yttrium *d*-orbitals contributing significantly to the electronic states at the Fermi level. The haeckelite phase shows enhanced conductivity due to its higher density of states. Formation energy calculations confirm the thermodynamic stability of both structures. Also, temperature-dependent transport properties revealed increasing electronic thermal conductivity and a nearly constant electrical conductivity above 50K, which are due to suppressed scattering phenomena at low temperatures. The Lorentz number, computed from the Wiedemann–Franz law, agrees with the theoretical metallic limit for the haeckelite phase across 50–300K, while the 2D YSe phase deviates at temperatures greater than 150K. Furthermore, the electronic molar specific heat varies linearly with temperature, consistent with classical predictions, and the Sommerfeld coefficients were determined for both phases. Our results underscore the potential of structural phase engineering in tailoring the electronic and thermal performance of nano materials.

Keywords: *Thermal conductivity, Electrical conductivity, Electronic structure, Lorentz number.*

Introduction

The characteristics of two-dimensional (2D) materials which result from low dimensionality compared to their bulk counterparts have completely changed the field of materials research. Their appearance have caused a paradigm change in material research, device technology, and condensed matter physics. Since graphene's revolutionary isolation by Novoselov *et al.*, (2004), a wide variety of 2D materials, such as transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), MXenes, group III–VI compounds, and rare-earth monochalcogenides, have garnered interest due to their potential uses in thermoelectrics, optoelectronics, and nanoelectronics (Omugbe *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2012; Radisavljevic *et al.* 2011). The discovery of semiconducting 2D TMDs such as MoS₂ and WS₂ revealed monolayer-induced band gap transitions from indirect to direct, with high on and off ratios in field-effect transistors (Wang *et al.*, 2012). However, the synthesis and theoretical prediction of its monolayer analogs have been made possible by developments in mechanical exfoliation, molecular beam epitaxy, and chemical vapor deposition (CVD). Due to variations in bonding geometry, symmetry, and dimensionality, the electronic structure and transport

characteristics of 2D and 3D phases may behave quite differently, making comparisons and contrasts crucial. Among the families of 2D materials, group III–VI compounds like InSe has competitive edge due to its piezoelectric properties, electronic responses, with high electron mobility (Goppalan *et al.*, 2019). Bandurin *et al.*, (2017) showed that monolayer InSe may be appropriate for quantum devices due to its anomalous optical properties and quantum Hall effect. When compared to symmetric structures, two-dimensional Janus materials have unique features that provide them a wide range of possible uses in the fabrication of electronic devices. Gao *et al.*, (2023) used first-principle simulations to study the electronic structure, optical, and photocatalytic properties of Janus materials. Their findings suggested that they might be very effective photocatalysts for water splitting because the internal electric field effect of the Janus structure reduces the possibility of recombination of the photo-generated electron-hole pair. The effect of the dielectric constant of free-carrier density, and of temperature on the transport properties of TMD were investigated (Goppalan *et al.*, 2022). Liao and coworkers (2025) used the DFT technique to investigate the electronic, transport, and

optoelectronic characteristics of 2D Ge_2Y_2 ($\text{Y} = \text{As}, \text{P}, \text{and N}$). semiconductors. Their results revealed the multi-functional properties of the monolayers with four atoms, indicating that they have a wide range of potential uses as flexible semiconductor devices. The properties of a material are greatly influenced by its structural phase. In thermoelectric applications, tetragonal phases in particular are known to give direction-dependent characteristics that might be beneficial. Recent research, for example, has thoroughly examined the structural differences of molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) and how they affect device performance and material properties. The optical, electronic and optoelectronic properties of bulk MoS_2 , monolayer, and multilayer forms have been thoroughly studied. Comparative analyses revealed notable differences in band structure and bandgap energy across these structures, which in turn influence light absorption and emission behaviours. In a variety of applications, MoS_2 has also shown great promise, especially in field-effect transistors, photovoltaics, and photodetectors (Zhou, 2024). Also, bandgaps and dielectric characteristics changed significantly when RbCaF_3 structure transition from cubic to tetragonal

symmetry (Ehsan et al., 2018). DFT and non-equilibrium Green's function (NEGF) techniques have been used to investigate the electronic transport characteristics of 2D tetragonal ZnX ($\text{X} = \text{S}, \text{Se}$) monolayers (Zhu, Meng, & Zhou, 2023). Tetragonal ZnSe and ZnS 2D structures have been shown by Zhu, Meng, & Zhou, (2023) to have outstanding electronic transport characteristics, which makes them eco-friendly and promising for use in a variety of electronic and optoelectronic devices. The structural phase-dependent characteristics of ZnTe , especially in its zinc-blende, wurtzite, and tetragonal forms, have been better understood via DFT investigations (Banat *et al.*, 2025). The three phases were confirmed to be semiconducting that show direct band gaps at the Γ -point, with reported values of 2.1 eV for the zinc-blende phase, 1.5 eV for the wurtzite phase, and 1.3 eV for the tetragonal phase. Electronic density of states studies showed that both Zn and Te orbitals contribute significantly to the valence and conduction bands, while the bonding properties vary significantly across phases. Modulating ZnTe electronic, optical and thermoelectric performance depends critically on these structural changes. Interestingly, the zinc-blende structure showed improved optical performance,

making it more appropriate for optoelectronic devices, while the tetragonal phase was found to be suitable for thermoelectric applications because of its advantageous transport characteristics (Banat *et al.*, 2025). Chegel, Behzad, & Ayeshe (2023) demonstrated that the thermal and electronic properties of tetragonal silicene could be significantly modulated by external electric and magnetic fields, illustrating the potential tunability of such phases.

Despite these advancements, rare-earth-based 2D materials remain underexplored. Yttrium monochalcogenides (YX; X = S, Se, Te) are rare-earth compounds that crystallize in the cubic rocksalt structure at ambient conditions and have attracted significant attention due to their structural, electronic, elastic, and superconducting properties (Bhardwaj & Singh, 2013; Hulliger & Hull, 1970; Seddik, *et al.*, 2010; Vaitheeswaran, *et al.* 2011). Sahoo *et al.* (2014) performed a thorough first-principles investigation of the electronic properties of Yttrium selenide (YSe), with emphasis on the lattice dynamics, elastic and structural stability of YSe under pressure. The rocksalt (B1) and CsCl-type (B2) crystallographic phases were the main subjects of their investigation. They found that a 32 GPa pressure induces

structural phase shift from B1 to B2 phase. In its ambient pressure B1 phase, YSe was shown to be an indirect bandgap semiconductor from the electronic band structures and density of states (DOS). On the other hand, the B2 phase showed metallic properties. The electronic structure's pressure-dependent transition highlights YSe tunable electronic behaviour, which makes it a promising option for phase-controlled electronic and thermoelectric applications. The lattice dynamics and thermodynamic properties of YSe, were investigated by Shinde *et al.* (2014) using DFT approach. The stability and electronic behaviour of the material were better understood through the electronic band structures and phonon dispersion interactions. Yttrium hydrogen selenide (YHSe) was the subject of a similar study by Aredo *et al.* (2024), which examined its electronic structure, phonon characteristics, and superconducting applications at different pressures. The energy bandgap and density of states close to the Fermi level decreased with increasing pressure, according to their findings, indicating increased electronic conductivity and possible superconductivity in YHSe material. Kumar *et al.* (2020) investigated 2D YSSe and reported the presence of

intrinsic magnetism and spin polarization originating from Y and chalcogen vacancies.

Our motivation is to investigate the electronic structure, thermal and electrical conductivity of 2D monolayer YSe and its tetragonal haeckelite phase using of DFT approach. By analyzing the impact of dimensionality and symmetry on the material's electronic behaviour, we seek to uncover insights into its potential roles in next-generation nanoelectronic devices. The organization of the remaining parts of the article is as follow: In section 2, the computational approach including the electronic structure and transport coefficients calculations will be presented. The results are discussed in section 3 while the conclusion is given in section 4.

Materials and Method

The foundation of contemporary computational materials research is the DFT method which provides precise and dependable predictions of the electronic structures of materials (Hohenberg & Kohn, 1964; Kohn & Sham, 1965). It makes it easier to evaluate important properties including band structure, carrier mobility, density of states (DOS), and thermoelectric coefficients all of which are necessary to determine if a material is suitable for real

world uses. DFT allows for a more thorough comprehension of thermal and electrical transport processes when combined with Boltzmann transport theory (Madsen & Singh, 2006). In this study, we used the DFT projector augmented plane wave (PAW) method embedded in the Quantum Espresso program (Giannozzi, *et al.* 2009; Giannozzi, *et al.* 2017). For the exchange-correlation functional, the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) version of the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) (Perdew, Burke & Ernzerhof, 1996) were applied.

A kinetic energy cutoff of 90Ry was applied to the wave function and 540Ry to the charge density and potential of the 2D YSe monolayer. We set 6×10^{-9} Ry as the convergence threshold for total energy. For structural optimization and total energy calculations, a 0.022Ry width smearing (Methfessel & Paxton, 1989) and a $12 \times 12 \times 1$ k-point grid (Monkhorst & Pack, 1976) was employed to sample the Brillouin zone. The density of states (DOS) and transport characteristics were calculated using the tetrahedron approach developed by Blöchl, Jepsen & Andersen, (1994) with a denser $35 \times 35 \times 1$ k-point grid. The interactions between periodic images were eliminated by introducing a vacuum separation of 28 Å along the c-axis. Atoms in the 2D YSe

monolayer occupy the Wyckoff locations a (0, 0, 1/2) and b (2/3, 1/3, 1/2) as it crystallizes in a trigonal symmetry (space group P3m1, No. 156). A kinetic energy cutoff of 85Ry was applied for the wave function and 510Ry for the charge density and potential for the tetragonal haeckelite-YSe (YSehl) structure. For the Brillouin zone sampling, a $6 \times 6 \times 4$ Monkhorst and Pack grid was employed. When the forces acting on atoms were less than 5×10^{-4} Ry/Bohr and the pressure was less than 0.5 kbar, structural relaxation was deemed to be complete. $16 \times 16 \times 14$ k-point grids were used to compute DOS and transport characteristics. The YSehl material crystallizes in a haeckelite-like (Tiling-lattice) tetragonal lattice with $P4_2/mmm$ symmetry, having inversion symmetry and two mirror planes. The 2D YSe and YSehl structures were visualized using XCRYSDEN (Kokalj, 2003). The formation energies per atom were calculated to validate thermodynamic stabilities via the fundamental equation given by

$$\Delta H_f = \frac{1}{p+q} (E(X_p Y_q) - pE(X) - qE(Y)) \quad (1)$$

where $E(XY)$, $E(X)$ and $E(Y)$ represent the total energies of the XY , the total energies of atoms X and Y in their bulk phases. For the Trigonal YSe monolayer, $p=q=1$ while for

the YSehl $p=q=4$. The structure of the studied materials are presented in Figure 1.

The electronic transport coefficients were obtained by solving the Boltzmann transport equations (Allen, 1996) within the constant relaxation time (τ) approximation (Madsen & Singh, 2006). In this approximation, the transport coefficients are obtained from the Boltzmann transport equations (Madsen & Singh, 2006; Allen, 1996)

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}(T, \mu) = \frac{1}{\Omega} \int \sigma_{\alpha\beta}(\epsilon) \left(\frac{-\partial f_{\mu}(T, \epsilon, \mu)}{\partial \epsilon} \right) d\epsilon \quad (2)$$

$$k_{\alpha\beta}(T, \mu) = \frac{1}{\Omega e T} \int \sigma_{\alpha\beta}(\epsilon) (-\mu)^2 \left(\frac{-\partial f_{\mu}(T, \epsilon, \mu)}{\partial \epsilon} \right) d\epsilon \quad (3)$$

where

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}(\epsilon) = \frac{e^2}{N} \sum_{i,k} \tau(i,k) v_{\alpha}(i,k) v_{\beta}(i,k) \delta(\epsilon - \epsilon(i,k)) \quad (4)$$

$$C(T, \mu) = \int n(\epsilon) (-\mu) \left(\frac{\partial f_{\mu}(T, \epsilon, \mu)}{\partial T} \right) d\epsilon \quad (5)$$

Indices α and β are tensor components, while Ω, μ and f are the unit cell volume, chemical potential, and the Fermi-Dirac distribution function respectively. The electronic charge and the number of k points in the Brillouin zone are denoted as e and N respectively. In Eq. (4), $v_{\alpha}(i,k)$ ($\alpha = x, y, z$) correspond to the α component of the group velocity of carriers at wave vector k

(Khazaei, *et al.*, 2014). The thermal and electrical conductivities are connected through the Wiedemann-Franz relation (Madsen & Singh, 2006)

$$k_{i,j}^{el} = \frac{\pi^2}{3} \left(\frac{k_B}{e} \right)^2 \sigma_{i,j} T \quad (6)$$

Figure 1 (a) 2D YSe with distance between the green-coloured atoms specifying the lattice constant. (b) The structure of tetragonal Haeckelite (YSehl) phase.

Results and Discussion

The electronic structure and transport properties of 2D YSe and its tetragonal haeckelite phase have been studied by means of DFT approach and the Boltzmann transport theory within the constant relaxation time approximation. The electronic structure revealed that both materials are metallic due to the transition of electrons from the valence band across the Fermi level. In Figures 2 and 3, the density of states (DOS) indicated that the electrons in the d-orbital of the Yttrium

element majorly contributes to the metallic conduction for both the 2D YSe and its haeckelite phase. However, the haeckelite form of YSe is most conductive due to its higher DOS. The formation energy energies presented in Table 1, show thermodynamic stability for both structures. The transport coefficients such as the electrical and electronic thermal conductivities were analyzed for the two materials. In Figures 2 and 3, the thermal conductivity increases with the increase in temperature from 50 to 300K

while the electrical conductivity decreases at low temperatures below 50K and become steady between temperature ranges of 50 to 300K. The steady behaviour may be ascribed to the absence of scattering phenomena at low temperature. Also, the metallic performance of the materials were determined by computing the Lorentz number (see Figure 4) from the Wiedemann-Franz law. This number for some metals has been predicted to deviate from the metallic limit value of $2.44 \times 10^{-8} \Omega W T^{-2}$ (Kumar, Prasad & Pohl, 1993). However, at the temperature range of 50 to 150K the 2D YSe aligns with the theoretic value of the Lorentz number but deviate at temperatures greater than 150K. In contrast, the tetragonal haeckelite phase maintains good agreement with the theoretical Lorenz number across the full temperature range (50–300 K), highlighting its robust metallic behaviour and underscoring the potential of

phase engineering to optimize material properties for electronic and thermal applications. The electronic specific heat capacities were analyzed for the structures as shown in Figure 5 (a, b). The electronic specific heat capacities vary linearly with the temperature ($C \propto T$) and increase with increase in temperature which is in agreement with classical theory. The constant of proportionality gives the Somerfield constant. By fitting the data, allows for the prediction of the Somerfield constants for the 2D YSe and it tetragonal haeckelite phase given in Table 1. It is worth mentioning that the results of the transport properties are limited to the electron-electron interactions and the scattering and phonon phenomena had not been considered. While the phonon interactions are dominant at high temperatures and may influence the transport coefficients, the transport properties at low temperatures were studied to obtain accurate results.

Table 1 Formation energy, equilibrium lattice constant and Somerfield constant of 2D YSe and it tetragonal Haeckelite phase.

Material	Lattice constant (Å)	Formation energy (eV/ per atom)	Somerfield constant ($mJ / Mo lK^2$)
YSe	$a = b = 4.70$	-2.71	8.2
YSehl	$a = b = 5.77, c = 5.71$	-10.56	10.2

Figure 2 (a) Band structure (b) Density of states of 2D YSe Trigonal phase, (c) Variations of electrical conductivity with temperature. (d) Variations of thermal conductivity with temperature. **Note** : $2E+14$ implies 2×10^{14} .

Figure 3 (a) Band structure (b) Density of states of YSe tetragonal haeckelite phase, (c) Variations of electrical conductivity with temperature. (d) Variations of thermal conductivity with temperature. **Note** : $6E+15$ implies 6×10^{15}

Figure 4 Variation of Lorentz number with temperature. (a) 2D YSe. (b) tetragonal haeckelite YSehl.
 Note: 2.5E-08 implies 2.5×10^{-8}

Figure 5 Variation of electronic specific heat capacity with temperature. (a) 2D YSe. (b) tetragonal haeckelite YSehl

Conclusion

In this study, the density functional theory and Boltzmann transport equations within the constant relaxation time approximation have been applied to investigate the electronic structure and transport properties of 2D YSe and its tetragonal haeckelite phase. Both phases exhibit metallic behavior, primarily driven by Yttrium d-orbital contributions at the Fermi level, with the haeckelite phase displaying enhanced conductivity due to a higher density of states. Thermodynamic stability was confirmed through formation energy calculations. Temperature-dependent transport analysis revealed increasing thermal conductivity and nearly temperature-independent electrical conductivity above 50K, suggesting minimal scattering effects in this regime. The Lorentz number analysis demonstrated that while 2D YSe aligns with the theoretical value only up to 150 K, the haeckelite phase maintains agreement across the full temperature range of 50-300K, confirming its robust metallicity. Additionally, the electronic specific heat followed a linear temperature dependence consistent with classical theory, and Sommerfeld coefficients were extracted for both structures. While phonon interactions were not included, limiting the transport analysis to low-temperature regimes enhances accuracy of the

results. These results highlight the potential of structural phase engineering in optimizing 2D materials for electronic and thermal applications.

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